

1 TITLE: On the use of multi-criteria decision analysis to formally integrate community values
2 into ecosystem-based freshwater management

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4 RUNNING TITLE: Community values in freshwater management

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16 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

17 SDL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
18 programme under the grant agreement No. 642317, the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant
19 agreement No. 748625, and from Hawke's Bay Regional Council. SCJ acknowledges
20 funding for the "GLANCE" project (Global Change Effects in River Ecosystems; 01
21 LN1320A) through the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). We
22 thank Fabiola C. Rodríguez Estrada for graphical support, and two anonymous referees, the
23 editor J. Price and additional editors for comments that considerably improved the
24 manuscript.

26 ABSTRACT

27 Freshwater ecosystems are essential to peoples' economic, cultural, and social wellbeing, yet
28 are still among the most threatened ecosystems on the planet. Consequently, a plethora of
29 recent regulations and policies seek to halt the loss of, restore, or safeguard freshwaters, their
30 biodiversity, and the ecosystem services they provide. Ecosystem-based management (EBM),
31 an approach that considers human society as an integral part of ecosystems, is increasingly
32 being promoted to help meet this challenge. EBM involves an overarching regulatory
33 framework and local solutions with trade-offs and compromises - factors that make decision
34 processes complex, but also provide the means for combining top-down regulation with
35 bottom-up priorities into collaborative management strategies. Although stakeholder
36 participation is encouraged in most modern freshwater management, community values are
37 often largely neglected. Here, we introduce a well-known participatory decision support
38 framework based on multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to operationalize EBM and
39 promote community-inclusive decision-making in freshwater management. We explain the
40 different steps that this approach comprises which lead to the prioritisation of a management
41 strategy in a collaborative way. We also show how cultural values that inherently embed
42 strong links between the environment and people, can be used together with typical
43 ecological and socio-economic values. We illustrate the MCDA-based EBM-approach for
44 New Zealand, one of the few countries in which regional freshwater management is
45 mandated to uphold environmental quality standards, while safeguarding local community
46 values and ecosystem services. Finally, we discuss some of the challenges which are
47 increasingly emerging as a result of mandated community collaboration in environmental
48 management.

49

50 KEY WORDS: bottom-up, community buy-in, collaborative, indigenous values, Māori,
51 multi-criteria decision analysis, MCDA, top-down

52 INTRODUCTION

53 Freshwater ecosystems are among the most threatened and modified environments on the
54 planet, with freshwater biodiversity decreasing more rapidly than in marine or terrestrial
55 systems (Vörösmarty et al., 2010; WWF, 2016). Healthy freshwater ecosystems are essential
56 for both maintaining biodiversity and for ensuring people’s economic, cultural, and social
57 wellbeing. Impacting these ecosystems has already led to, and will further increase, the loss
58 of water-based ecosystem services (ES) people receive from them (Russi et al., 2013).
59 Current national and international water and environmental regulations (e.g. the European
60 Union’s Water Framework Directive (WFD; 2000/60/EC), the EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy
61 (COM/2011/244 final) and the Convention on Biological Diversity) mandate the
62 management of freshwater ecosystems in a way that acknowledges social-ecological
63 interactions, rather than treating society and the environment as separate entities.

64 Ecosystem-based management (EBM) is increasingly proposed as an approach that can
65 incorporate such interactions. There is no agreed-upon definition of EBM, but it can
66 generally be understood as a collaborative-management (often referred to as co-management)
67 approach intended to restore, enhance, and/or protect the resilience of an ecosystem so as to
68 sustain or improve the flow of ES and to conserve biodiversity, while considering human
69 society as an integral part of that ecosystem (Long, Charles, & Stephenson, 2015).

70 Progressing from economic/environmentally-driven management to management that
71 also considers social drivers and implications requires change. Governance modes and local
72 and national policies have to shift from top-down regulation to more bottom-up, local
73 decision-making structures, involving stakeholder entities interested in the management
74 decisions. The WFD, for example, mandates each EU member state to plan freshwater
75 improvement in river basin management plans (European Commission, 2012), which should
76 be prepared and updated in participatory processes that inform and consult with interested
77 stakeholder entities (European Commission, 2003). Similarly, the United States’ Clean Water
78 Act pursues the objective of maintaining and restoring aquatic ecological integrity and
79 expects stakeholder participation to contribute to developing, revising, and enforcing
80 regulations and management plans (Federal Water Pollution Control Act, 1948).

81 Despite such regulations, so far most management approaches have mainly focused on
82 integrating top-down environmental and economic values, whereas cultural values and local
83 knowledge have received little attention in practice (Daniel et al., 2012). Here we consider
84 cultural values to be “non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems through spiritual
85 enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation and aesthetic experience”
86 (Robertson, 2004). Management decisions that relegate cultural values to an afterthought

87 have been criticized by ecologists who perceive intrinsic values in nature (Redford & Adams,
88 2009) and by theorists who are critical towards commodification of nature (Salmond, Tadaki,
89 & Gregory, 2014). Cultural values are often location-specific and, therefore, they may not be
90 adequately considered by regionally- and nationally-mandated regulations. Consequently, we
91 argue that future environmental decision making for freshwater management could greatly
92 benefit from a more explicit and more structured incorporation of cultural community values
93 than at present. How to effectively do this is the subject of this paper.

94 Examples of cultural values people relate to fresh waters can include swimming, boating,
95 angling, feeling calmed, inspired, happy and/or energized when spending time at, on, or in, a
96 freshwater body or experiencing its beauty etc. There are two main challenges when
97 including cultural values in structured, analytical decision making. Firstly, many have argued
98 that these values are incommensurate and not amenable to economic trade-offs (Miller, Tait,
99 & Saunders, 2015). For example, a management action may be seen as violating a deeply
100 held principle and, therefore, the use of trade-offs is rejected, stalling progress in
101 collaborative decision making. Secondly, cultural values are often difficult to articulate and
102 quantify.

103 Many of the problems in natural resource management, including the development of
104 community-inclusive freshwater EBM strategies, are so-called ‘wicked problems’ (Parrott,
105 2017). Problems are considered as ‘wicked’, if there is no single, optimal, or clear solution
106 (*sensu* Rittel & Webber (1973)) due to inherent competing or conflicting interests and
107 ‘different ways of knowing’ (i.e. unrecognized contextual, methodological, and substantive
108 differences among knowledge systems; *sensu* Brugnach & Ingram (2012)). Consequently, in
109 the absence of clearly structured and well-communicated processes, EBM can be co-opted
110 (Duncan, 2013). This challenge can, however, be overcome with well-designed processes that
111 are flexible, adaptive, and include scenario development and evaluation (Sterling et al.,
112 2017). Hence, there is an urgent need for a support framework based on collaborative
113 decisions that is (i) transparent, (ii) allows for stakeholders’ ecological, socio-economic, and
114 cultural values to be quantified and accounted for, (iii) allows for the concurrent
115 consideration of top-down and bottom-up defined values, (iv) can mathematically test and
116 compare outcomes of different management alternatives, and (v) can ultimately prioritise
117 management actions with collective buy-in, (vi) while accounting for uncertainty. Statutory
118 promotion of such a framework would assure its implementation and provide opportunities to
119 further refine it.

120 Here, we introduce Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) as a participatory
121 structured decision support tool, and outline the ten iterative steps that can facilitate the

122 formal development of a freshwater management plan. We then show how MCDA allows for
123 mixed collaboration, i.e. the concurrent inclusion of top-down environmental regulatory
124 limits as well as bottom-up, locally-defined community values and preferences. We show
125 how New Zealand's current approach to freshwater management is compatible with such a
126 framework. Finally, we discuss the potential of MCDA to benefit EBM by strengthening the
127 prospects of mixed collaborative approaches.

128 129 MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS (MCDA)

130 Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is a generic term for a collection of theories and
131 approaches which offer support in complex decision situations facing multiple, conflicting
132 objectives and large uncertainty (Eisenführ, Weber, & Langer, 2010). MCDA decomposes
133 these complex decision situations into manageable parts to help systematically evaluate and
134 prioritize management alternatives. Thereby, the relative importance of the goals of the
135 decision situation is defined through weights that represent stakeholders' preferences.
136 Management alternatives are evaluated and ranked based on their predicted consequences for
137 each goal, incorporating trade-offs among these consequences and measures of uncertainty.

138 During the last decade, MCDA has gained popularity in helping with river management
139 decisions. Reichert et al. (2015) proposed a conceptual framework for environmental decision
140 support that employs the best available scientific knowledge to identify management
141 alternatives with the highest likelihood to achieve ecological, economic, and societal goals.
142 As a hypothetical case study they conducted a spatial river restoration prioritisation for a
143 small river catchment in Switzerland. Comino et al. (2016) applied spatial MCDA to support
144 policy and action definition for managing the Pellice river basin in Italy. Langhans et al.
145 (2016) found that four MCDA-elements which are often simplified in river restoration
146 assessments, due to time and/or resource constraints, do not reflect experts' opinions and
147 should therefore be avoided in implementations. And most recently, Paillex et al. (2017) used
148 MCDA to assess and compare the ecological quality of a restored and an unrestored river
149 reach in Switzerland.

150 Among the range of different MCDA methodologies, multi-attribute value theory and
151 multi-attribute utility theory (MAVT/MAUT) are increasingly used for environmental
152 management (Reichert et al., 2015). A range of properties make these theories especially
153 interesting for freshwater management (Paillex et al., 2017): (i) They are based on axioms of
154 rational choice which is useful when decisions have to be justified (e.g., to the taxpayers or
155 the public in general), (ii) they focus explicitly on the goals that should be achieved through
156 the implementation of a management plan and not on the selection of the management action

157 itself; (iii) new management actions can be included at any stage of the decision process
158 without triggering a change in the ranking of the already included alternatives, (iv) they can
159 consider uncertainties, for example of the environmental assessment, the prediction of the
160 consequences of management actions, or the stakeholder preferences, (v) they can take risk
161 attitudes of stakeholders into account in the form of utility functions, and (vi) they
162 accommodate a combination of ecological, socio-economic, and cultural management goals.

164 TEN STEPS TO A MCDA-DRIVEN EBM-FRESHWATER MANAGEMENT PLAN

165 To facilitate communication with stakeholder entities, we have split the MCDA-process into
166 ten discrete steps adapted from Reichert et al. (2015), as shown in Figure 1.

167 **Steps A and B: Problem framing and stakeholder analysis.** The first step in making an
168 informed decision is to clearly define the problem, i.e. the main goal (Step A). For freshwater
169 management this could involve identifying a management strategy for the respective
170 freshwater system that considers regulations and has buy-in from the community. The
171 relevant stakeholders who are to be involved in tackling the problem are then identified (Step
172 B), possibly using snowball sampling. For freshwater management, relevant stakeholders
173 could include representatives of the local government responsible for managing fresh waters,
174 local indigenous groups, farmers, fishermen, agriculture industry, tourism, kayakers/canoers,
175 yachting clubs, conservation groups, the local community, etc. Steps A and B can usually be
176 prepared by the facilitator before the first stakeholder workshop. However, the details need to
177 be confirmed (or reframed) and additional stakeholders might need to be identified during the
178 initial workshop.

179 **Step C and D: Identifying values, sub-goals, and attributes.** Sub-goals are desired
180 outcomes of the decision process (e.g. increased fish harvest from a lake) and are either
181 derived from environmental directives (compulsory, environmental goals) or are identified by
182 stakeholders, thereby reflecting their values (i.e. activities, uses, sources of value, or “things
183 that matter”; Step C). The sub-goals can then be arranged, possibly divided into more specific
184 sub-goals, and organized in a hierarchy (Step D₁). The hierarchy should only contain distinct
185 goals to avoid double counting. Additionally, the sub-goals should conform with preference
186 independence, meaning that preferences for the level of one sub-goal can be specified
187 independently of the level of other sub-goals (Eisenführ et al., 2010). The splitting of goals
188 into sub-goals allows to identify and assign attributes to the most explicitly defined sub-goals
189 at the bottom of the hierarchy. Attributes are measurable system properties or indicators
190 (Steps D₂). If a sub-goal is difficult to measure, a proxy attribute can be used. Steps C and D
191 can be undertaken with all stakeholders in a workshop format. Different techniques, such as

192 working with sticky-notes, can be used to make sure that all stakeholders have a voice in the
 193 workshops.

194
 195 **Figure 1.** Infographic showing the ten different steps adopted in the community-driven
 196 decision making process based on Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA).

197 **Step E: Quantifying value preferences and weights of goals.** MCDA focuses on value
198 scores to prioritise management actions rather than asking stakeholders directly which action
199 they prefer. Mathematically identifying priority actions can lead to surprising results. For
200 example, when stakeholder's initial preferred management action does not end up being the
201 best action to safeguard her/his priority values after prioritization is based on her/his
202 quantified values. To be able to calculate the value scores based on all attributes, the
203 fulfilment of the sub-goals has to be quantified as a function of the attributes. This is done by
204 identifying a scoring function for each attribute (Fig. 2). Scoring functions have a continuous
205 scale of 0 to 1 on the y-axis and the considered range of the attribute on the x-axis (0 = no
206 achievement, 1 = full achievement of the sub-goal). The functions can either be translated
207 from already established assessment protocols, for example to conform with compulsory
208 goals (see below). They can also be elicited from stakeholders in interviews, for example
209 using the mid-value splitting method (Lienert, Koller, Konrad, McArdeell, & Schuwirth,
210 2011). Interviews should follow a strict protocol to minimize biases due to framing,
211 availability, and social context (Burgman et al., 2011). The shape of each scoring function
212 reflects the stakeholders' preferences on how each attribute relates to each sub-goal. Where
213 multiple scoring functions are elicited for the same attribute for the same stakeholder group,
214 and have to be pooled to represent a summary of this group's opinion, a variety of
215 combination methods can be used (e.g., Stewart & Quintana, 2018).

216 Scoring functions describe stakeholders' preferences regarding certain attribute outcomes,
217 whereas utility functions describe preferences in relation to risky ones. Utility functions can
218 either be directly elicited from stakeholders or converted from scoring functions after
219 accounting for the stakeholders' attitudes towards risk (Dyer & Sarin, 1982).

220 Stakeholders also define the relative importance of sub-goals by assigning weights to each
221 of them. For example, a stakeholder might decide to give a high weight to one of the sub-
222 goals to indicate a preference for this goal. Assigning a weight of zero results in the exclusion
223 of the respective sub-goal for the respective stakeholder. Again, this process is done by
224 following a standardized protocol (Step E). A common method for the elicitation of weights
225 is the (reverse) swing method explained in (Lienert et al., 2011). Where multiple weights for
226 the same sub-goal for the same stakeholder group are identified, these can be combined using
227 different weighting schemes to represent the group's opinion (Cooke, ElSaadany, & Huang,
228 2008).

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Figure 2. Example of the quantification of value preferences in the form of a scoring function. Scoring functions have a continuous scale from 0 to 1 on the y-axis and the considered range of the attribute in its original unit on the x-axis (0 = no achievement, 1 = full achievement of the goal). This step of the MCDA process is excluded from the main infographic, since it is the most complex one, requiring more detailed explanation.

Steps F and G: Identifying management actions and predicting outcomes for each alternative. Stakeholders identify potential management actions (Step F). How each attribute will change with each of the potential actions is then projected or predicted based on environmental system models or expert judgement, respectively (Step G).

Step H: Combining steps E and G to calculate the value of each management action for each stakeholder entity. Predicted attribute levels for each alternative management action are standardized to a value between 0 to 1 based on the stakeholder-specific scoring functions. Values are then aggregated up the hierarchy to an overall value for each action, considering stakeholder-specific weightings of the sub-goals. Thereby, the weighted arithmetic mean should be used to aggregate values of redundant sub-goals, which are often found at the lower level of the hierarchy (Langhans, Schuwirth, & Reichert, 2014). Aggregating additively allows for compensation (i.e. a good value can, to some degree, compensate a bad one when aggregated), and therefore increases the statistical significance of

249 the results. Sub-goals that are complementary to each other (such as those often found at
250 higher levels of the hierarchy) should be aggregated with a mixture of additive and minimum
251 aggregation (also called worst case or one-out, all-out) to allow for some compensation but
252 yet still penalize for sub-goals with a very low score (Langhans et al., 2014).

253 **Step I: Ranking the alternatives for each stakeholder, addressing conflicts, and**
254 **finding a commonly approved solution.** For each stakeholder the actions are ranked
255 according to decreasing overall score. The stakeholder-specific rankings of the potential
256 actions are then discussed among all participating parties in a workshop. At this stage, the
257 insights gained by going together through the described process facilitates agreement on one
258 or more of the management actions, or the identification of a new, compromise solution to
259 the management problem.

260 **Step J: Identifying key knowledge gaps.** Having performed the previous nine steps,
261 knowledge gaps will have become apparent. Any new knowledge gained can be included in
262 the MCDA through iteration, where each iteration allows making better-informed decisions.

264 MCDA FOR NEW ZEALANDS' FRESHWATER MANAGEMENT

265 *Background to freshwater management in NZ*

266 In 1991, New Zealand (NZ) adopted an integrated approach to freshwater management
267 (Resource Management Act, 1991), which has recently been further developed in the
268 National Policy Statement for Freshwater Management (NPS-FM; NZ Ministry for the
269 Environment, 2017). Compared to the previous approach, the NPS-FM recognizes diverse
270 elements of freshwater use that contribute to wellbeing in society. Hence, to conform with the
271 NPS-FM, the next generation of management plans must consider values that are important
272 to the community as well as compulsory water quality and health limits. Consequently, future
273 NZ freshwater management plans will combine governmental and community objectives.
274 Currently, freshwater management plans are developed for each of the 16 regions in NZ.

275 NZ is one of the many countries around the world where fresh waters are of major
276 importance to indigenous people. To Māori water is a tupuna (ancestor), which is why it is
277 considered a taonga (treasure). In addition, waterways provide resources for cultural products
278 such as mahinga kai, which is a Māori term for traditional food and resource gathering (Tipa
279 & Teirney, 2003). Hence, fresh water is crucial in maintaining Māori traditions and
280 knowledge (Harmsworth, Young, Walker, Clapcott, & James, 2011). Following the
281 international trend to increasingly include indigenous communities as active participants in
282 environmental decision making, NZ's local and central governments are eager to engage with
283 Māori groups (iwi/ hapū) in freshwater management planning processes (Harmsworth et al.,

284 2016). Actually, legal requirement to do so is given by the Treaty of Waitangi, which is the
285 foundation document of Māori rights. The NPS-FM takes up the Treaty mandate by
286 specifically considering Māori's water values separately from other community values (see
287 below) and by emphasizing on iwi/hapū to play a key part as partners in the participatory
288 freshwater-management planning-process.

289

290 *Applying steps D and E of the MCDA-framework to the NPS-FM*

291 The NPS-FM sets out 13 national values and uses for fresh water. Two of them are
292 compulsory when developing a freshwater management plan: (i) ecosystem health and (ii)
293 public health and recreation (NZ Ministry for the Environment 2017). For the eleven
294 remaining national values, the goals, attributes, and their measurement methods will be
295 defined by the local community. Figure 3 shows how the compulsory national values and the
296 non-compulsory values described in the NPS-FM could be structured hierarchically
297 according to step D of the MCDA process (Fig. 1). Additional goals and corresponding
298 attributes identified by iwi and stakeholders during the MCDA-process can be included in the
299 hierarchy either as a new high level goal, or under one of the existing branches of the
300 hierarchy.

301 The NPS-FM defines attributes for the compulsory values/goals: Seven attributes to
302 measure ecosystem health ('phytoplankton', 'total Nitrogen', 'total Phosphorus',
303 'periphyton', 'Nitrate', 'Ammonia', 'dissolved Oxygen') and two attributes ('cyanobacteria',
304 'E. coli') to assess whether water quality does not harm people's health, when they use water
305 bodies for recreational purposes (Fig. 3).

306
 307 **Figure 3.** Objectives hierarchy of compulsory national values (in solid boxes) and other
 308 suggested, but non-compulsory values (in dashed boxes) to include when developing

309 freshwater co-management strategies in New Zealand. The sub-goals in bold are the headings
310 of the 13 value categories outlined in the National Policy Statement for Freshwater
311 Management (NPS-FM).

312
313 The NPS-FM provides quality bands for the nine attributes that can be used to establish
314 scoring functions for each of the attributes (c.f., step E, Fig. 2; see Langhans et al. (2013) for
315 a complete description of how to transfer quality assessments into scoring functions). For the
316 attributes 'phytoplankton', 'total Nitrogen', 'total Phosphorus', 'periphyton', 'Nitrate',
317 'Ammonia', 'dissolved Oxygen' and 'cyanobacteria' (Fig. 4 a-h), the NPS-FM defines four
318 quality bands (A-D). For the attribute 'E. coli', which is a proxy attribute for assessing
319 swimmability of fresh waters (Fig. 4 i and j), five quality bands were developed. Following
320 other national water quality assessment protocols that use scoring functions (Niederberger et
321 al., 2016), we assumed that each quality band stands for the same increase in quality and,
322 therefore, in freshwater value (0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0 for a-h; and 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1 for i
323 and j). According to the NPS-FM, the national bottom line lies between the quality bands C
324 and D (band D is deemed unacceptable), which consequently corresponds to a value of ≤ 0.25
325 (a-h), while there is no simple national bottom line set for the attribute 'swimmability'.

326 Minimum values ($y = 0$) of a scoring function represent the worst possible condition of the
327 attribute in the respective freshwater system, while maximum values ($y = 1$) represent the
328 best possible condition (Fig. 4). Since minimum and maximum values are not defined in the
329 NPS-FM, they were defined for this exercise by an expert with extensive experience in NZ
330 freshwater ecology (M. Schallenberg, University of Otago). However, the definition of
331 minimum and maximum values for the compulsory national values as well as assigning
332 values to the quality bands should be verified and confirmed more generally before using the
333 MCDA process to design freshwater management plans. Scoring functions for attributes that
334 measure the non-mandatory values have to be elicited from stakeholders.

335

337 **Figure 4.** Scoring functions for the attributes that quantify the compulsory national values
338 translated from the National Policy Statement for Freshwater Management (NPS-FM).

339
340 *The role of experts in the MCDA process*

341 The NPS-FM aims to maintain all freshwater ecosystems in a healthy ecological state and to
342 restore those that are degraded from such a state (NZ Ministry for the Environment, 2017).
343 For iwi and stakeholders, it can be difficult to identify all relevant sub-goals and measurable
344 system attributes as well as to quantify the degree of fulfillment of the sub-goals as a function
345 of the attributes (Reichert et al., 2015). Therefore, Reichert et al. recommend that this part of
346 the hierarchy is elicited from experts (i.e. freshwater ecologists) or translated from existing
347 procedures, as we show here using the quality assessments given in the NPS-FM for the
348 different attributes. Where experts are relied on to define sub-goals, attributes, and scoring
349 functions, these elements should be carefully explained to the participating iwi and
350 stakeholders, so that they can assign weights to all sub-goals in an informed way.

351 Another important role experts can play in the MCDA process is to help iwi and
352 stakeholders identifying potential management alternatives. Iwi and stakeholders might not
353 be aware of, or up-to-date with, the latest available technologies and management actions.
354 Experts also develop and apply conceptual and quantitative models to project the
355 consequences of the potential management actions. Where sufficient data to construct
356 quantitative models is unavailable, experts' system knowledge can be elicited to predict the
357 potential effects of the management alternatives (Reichert et al., 2015).

358 Finally, the development of the freshwater management plan should be set up and
359 supervised by an expert in decision support theory (i.e., in MAVT and MAUT in our case), if
360 an MCDA process is employed. This will ensure that tools and methods are applied
361 according to the newest literature and that input data and therefore the respective outcomes
362 are as unbiased, accurate, and inclusive as possible.

363 All of the above expert roles are universal and independent of the MCDA-application
364 location. Considering that NZ mandates community input into freshwater management
365 (which includes the definition of sub-goals for the ecosystem state by the community),
366 experts must play an additional, crucial role: educating the community about biodiversity,
367 ecological structure, and ecosystem functioning prior to the MCDA process, to help iwi and
368 stakeholders build informed preferences.

369
370 **DISCUSSION**

371 EBM is complex, because it involves community participation and local solutions with trade-

372 offs and compromises within an overarching regulatory framework (Kiker, Bridges,
373 Varghese, Seager, & Linkov, 2005). This complexity also reflects the need to simultaneously
374 integrate mandated freshwater values with locally-defined limits and community priorities, as
375 it is currently required for freshwater management in NZ (NZ Ministry for the Environment
376 2017). Combining top-down regulations with bottom-up participation in a community-
377 inclusive approach has been suggested to be the optimal approach to deal with environmental
378 management challenges (Khadka & Vacik, 2012). Therefore, an MCDA-based decision
379 support framework has the potential to facilitate the development of freshwater EBM in
380 multiple ways:

- 381 • MCDA entails a formal process with a long track record in social science. It can therefore
382 draw information and experience from an extensive literature reflecting many case studies.
- 383 • MCDA is mostly community-driven, assisted by experts informing the decision support
384 process, and facilitators leading the community through the different steps. It is important
385 to note that facilitators are neutral and do not contribute their values and preferences to the
386 process.
- 387 • The different steps of the MCDA process are transparent; the model structure, shapes of
388 value/utility functions and weightings given to the input data are clearly observable to
389 stakeholders. This understanding creates trust in the decision recommendation and
390 promotes commitment in implementing management actions. Moreover, transparency
391 fosters learning by, for example, allowing the collaborative exploration of how changes in
392 input values and preferences can influence the prioritization of the management actions
393 (Salo & Hämäläinen, 2010).
- 394 • The discrete steps in the decision support process can easily be iterated when new
395 knowledge is available. It is therefore compliant with the concept of adaptive
396 management.
- 397 • During the process of developing an MCDA-based EBM plan, the integrities of both
398 subjective freshwater values and objective freshwater system knowledge are maintained.
399 These components are only combined at the end of the process, when prioritising the
400 optimal management actions for the involved entities. Hence, the prioritisation is based on
401 a purely mathematical calculation and is, therefore, immune to power dynamics among
402 stakeholders.
- 403 • The process embodies information sharing and communication across iwi/ hapū,
404 stakeholders and decision makers during multiple workshops, which supports the
405 convergence of opinion and ideas. Social learning is the recognition that people learn

406 through active adaptation of their existing knowledge in response to their experiences with
407 other people and their environment (Allen et al., 2011). Hence, it is likely that information
408 sharing is also beneficial for fostering compromise solutions in freshwater management,
409 where multiple ways of knowing and multiple types of knowledge must be incorporated
410 into the decision making process.

- 411 • The prioritisation of management actions is the focus of the MCDA-based EBM approach.
412 Outputs of the EBM-MCDA process can, therefore, directly lead to the development of
413 catchment management plans with high levels of community buy-in.
- 414 • The MCDA-based EBM approach can consider both values that have been mandated (e.g.,
415 National water quality guidelines) and community-defined, bottom-up values, including
416 difficult-to-quantify, cultural values. In addition, MCDA allows the consideration of
417 indigenous values such as for example *mahinga kai* as a value for food provisioning
418 separately from *mahinga kai* as a cultural value.

419

420 *Challenges for MCDA-based freshwater EBM in NZ*

421 There is ample literature discussing potential challenges that might need to be tackled when
422 using MCDA (e.g., Reichert et al., 2015). Common challenges, which can also not be
423 overcome when applying best practice, include i) the time-consuming nature of working
424 through the process, especially the elicitation of scoring functions, ii) traditional decision
425 makers (e.g., environmental authorities) may not be interested in participating in the process
426 or in providing information to it, and iii) the MCDA process does not necessarily identify a
427 single, best management action for all stakeholders. It is up to stakeholders and decision
428 makers as to whether the outcome of the process leads to an overall agreement on one of the
429 actions or to a compromise solution. The process can only be successful, if participants are
430 willing to collaborate in a consensus-seeking spirit. Besides these challenges, we identified
431 four additional ones that might be specifically relevant for NZ, which we elaborate on below.

432

433 Finding agreement within stakeholder groups

434 MCDA processes commonly start with the identification of different stakeholder groups that
435 have an interest in, or are affected by, the decision making. Doing so is based on the
436 assumption that all individuals of such a group have the same, or very similar, preferences.
437 Involving the community in freshwater management planning leads to the challenge that '*the*
438 *community*' is likely not a stakeholder group with homogenous preferences, but one with
439 interpersonal differences and goal incongruities (Matsatsinis, Grigoroudis, & Samaras, 2005).
440 A way forward in this case is to apply factor or cluster analysis to base the assignment of '*the*

441 *community*' (as well as all other participants) to specific stakeholder groups based on their
442 preferences, i.e. how they weight the different sub-goals (Spath, 1980). Examples of
443 stakeholder groups emerging from a cluster analysis could be '*spiritualists*' (people of the
444 community who believe the freshwater system should be in a healthy condition because of
445 ethical reasons), '*sustainable users*' (people who have an economic interest in fresh water
446 and want to use it sustainably), '*fresh water recreationists*' (people who want the freshwater
447 system to be in a good enough status and equipped with the necessary infrastructure to enjoy
448 a freshwater-based recreational activity) and so on.

449

450 Power sharing

451 MCDA is based on the assertion that all parties (whether they are in positions of power to
452 make decisions about the environment or not) that are interested in the decision problem
453 should be part of the decision making process. Where there are power imbalances, it could be
454 decided a priori that decision making will be shared equitably among all of the parties (i.e.,
455 strong co-management, *sensu* Taiepa et al. (1997)). This form of co-management is distinct
456 from a process where iwi and stakeholders develop a management plan that serves as a
457 recommendation to the decision maker. A major risk of such a non-equitable decision
458 approach is the creation of consultation fatigue, if the recommendation is not, or not enough,
459 considered by the decision authority (Reed, 2008). Poor personal reward or little capacity to
460 influence decisions may result in iwi and stakeholders not being willing to participate in
461 future projects. Hence to make the collaboration process as successful as possible and to
462 increase the likelihood that a co-developed management plan is implemented successfully,
463 the decision makers (e.g., the environmental authorities) should participate in good faith in
464 the MCDA process. This challenge might be aggravated in regions where iwi/hapū find their
465 partner role in the collaboration process not being appropriately acknowledged and protected,
466 despite the Treaty of Waitangi and its principles being embraced in current NZ legislation
467 and policy.

468

469 Social learning

470 Inclusive workshops are crucial to bring people with different preferences together, so they
471 can share their values and opinions. Doing so can lead to a learning process which may
472 ultimately facilitate compromise solutions (Brymer, Wulforth, & Brunson, 2018). In NZ, a
473 parallel process to freshwater management where Māori are given the space to carry out their
474 own identification of values, weights, and attributes - reflecting a Treaty partnership process -
475 has been advocated (Robb, Harmsworth, & Awatere, 2015). The application of such a

476 parallel process will likely reduce the benefits of social learning as compared to an inclusive
477 MCDA-based process. However, MCDA is flexible enough to accommodate such structuring
478 of the decision-making process, where otherwise freshwater management planning would be
479 stalled. The focus of this study is on policy development.

480

481 Trust building

482 Like any other participatory decision and planning process, an MCDA-based decision
483 process heavily relies on forming trusted relationships (Heldt et al., 2016). In NZ, this trust
484 needs to be built between the stakeholder groups and the institutions with the authority to
485 make decisions which affect freshwater management (i.e. the Crown (NZ Government)
486 and/or Regional Councils) but also among the various stakeholder groups. Additionally, the
487 quality of the relationships between iwi/hapū and all the other participants will likely play a
488 significant role in the success of the participation process and, therefore, in developing a co-
489 management plan (Harmsworth & Awatere, 2013).

490

491 CONCLUSIONS

492 There is an increasing awareness that environmental decisions, and therewith biological and
493 cultural diversity, can benefit from the inputs of local and indigenous knowledge (Gavin et
494 al., 2015) as well as from community buy-in. NZ's NPS-FM is therefore consistent with
495 international regulations and initiatives, which increasingly mandate community involvement
496 in environmental management. However, the implementation of processes to achieve this has
497 lacked guidance and consistency among NZ Regional Councils, which must implement the
498 policies. The MCDA-based approach we propose here is a helpful tool to facilitate greater
499 community involvement in NZ's freshwater management and to potentially guide policy
500 development. Although we applied it to a NZ case study, this approach has general
501 applicability for including community preferences in environment decision making.

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